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Leaving the parental home in Italy during the economic crisis

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition to adulthood is a complex process involving several steps that include the completion of school education, the entry into the labour market, leaving the parental home, union formation and parenthood (Hogan and Astone, 1986; Goldscheider and Goldscheider, 1993). The prolonged permanence in the family of origin is considered connected with high levels of unemployment, precarious work and the low wages earned when young people enter the labour market in Europe (Iacovou, 2010). This is particularly true when describing the Italian context where young adults show the most relevant delay in home leaving in comparison to the other European countries. The role of the economic constraints, due to lack of opportunities for new generations, especially in finding a stable job, combined with a welfare system not particularly generous towards young people represent one of the main explanations for that delay (Alfieri *et al.*, 2015). In the last decades, the new social risks particularly affected the young Italian cohorts in terms of “precarious employment, unstable and carousel careers and (...) exclusion from welfare entitlements” (Barbieri, 2011). This situation generates insecurity and uncertainty about the future, with a consequent tendency to postpone choices that entail the assumption of responsibilities (Micheli and Rosina, 2009). If economic constraints and difficulties in finding a stable job tend to have a negative impact on the transition process to adulthood and on family formation, the recent economic crisis, which occurred between 2008 and 2013, may be expected to worsen further the youth’s conditions. These facts contribute to exacerbate social inequalities (Gini 1909) and induce an additional delay in young Italians’ life course paths (Carcillo *et al.*, 2015).

The scientific literature is rich of studies which address the impact of the Great Recession on individual fertility choices (Goldstein *et al.*, 2013), but there is a lack of research on the effects of the economic downturn on previous crucial life course events such as the departure from the parental home.

Since Italy is one of the countries that has been characterized by the longest permanence of young adults in the parental home (Ferrari *et al.*, 2014), even before the beginning of the Great Recession, it is particularly

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interesting to evaluate to which extent the crisis had an impact on the achievement of a residential autonomy.

In order to capture the effect of the crisis, in our paper we focus on the short term intentions of leaving the parental home. Positive intentions of living away are considered the premise in the achievement of a residential autonomy, while an increase in negative intentions tends to produce a postponement of further steps in the transition process to adulthood.

Pooling together data from the survey “Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective” carried out by the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) in 2007 (the year before the beginning of the Great Recession), and the data from the survey “Youth Project” carried out in the mid-2012 by the Toniolo Institute for Advanced Studies and IPSOS, we are able to compare conditions and expectations before and during the Great Recession of young adults aged between 21 and 29.

The paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the background literature while section 3 illustrates the data used; then we illustrate the empirical model in section 4. In section 5 we comment the results obtained and section 6 concludes.

2. BACKGROUND

According to Theory of Planned Behaviour (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1991) the decision of realizing a behaviour that is under volitional control is anticipated by the formation of positive intentions toward that behaviour.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour was developed to predict the intention toward that behaviour and aims to explain all behaviour over which individuals are able to exert control. It asserts that the realization of a specific behaviour is anticipated by the formation of positive intentions to perform a given behaviour. The formation of positive intentions is in turn the consequence of several determinants, such as ideational and background factors that include both material constraints and value orientations.

While value orientations are supposed to be relatively stable in time and may change only in a long-run perspective (Lesthaeghe and Moors, 2002) material conditions are more subjected to modifications due to macroeconomics shocks or changes of individual life course paths. Hence, in this study, we focus only on the effect of material conditions, given the assumption that values were more stable in such a small time window (nevertheless, the assumption does not deny the crucial importance of attitudes, social norms and value orientations in orienting the timing of life course events). Our aim is to compare the change in the intentions of leaving the parental home in a limited time horizon (only five years separate the two samples analysed). Changes in the economic and social context may favour or obstacle the formation of positive intentions towards

certain behaviour. Our specific purpose in this paper is to study the decision-making process of leaving the parental home through a comparison between the intentions before and the after the beginning of “The Great Recession”.

With respect to the formation of the intentions towards the departure from the family of origin, recent literature confirmed the importance of both socio-economic and cultural factors.

Focusing on the effect of cultural factors, as shown nowadays in several well-researched studies (see, in particular, Reher, 1998), Southern European countries show “stronger” family ties compared to Northern ones, which are characterized by early home leaving. Indeed, Southern European countries are marked by solid relationships between parents and children (Dalla Zuanna and Micheli, 2004) that often provide emotional support and material supply when young adults become autonomous. On one hand this process is due to the strength of cultural patterns of family loyalties, allegiances, and authority; on the other hand strong family ties were developed in response to an inefficient welfare system in order to provide material support to the weakest members of the family. This means that parents’ social conditions have here a central role in determining the timing of the departure of their children (De Long Gierveld *et al.*, 1991; Rosina and Fraboni, 2004; De Marco and Cosner Berzin, 2008). In particular, the possibility of family support has been seen as a critical factor involving the choice of leaving home (Santarelli and Cottone, 2009) and influencing the choice of cohabiting (Di Giulio and Rosina, 2007).

For what concerns the material determinants of the intentions of leaving home most of the literature concentrated on employment conditions. The effects of income and the employment status have been emphasized and considered as the key predictors of the likelihood of leaving home. Preferences on the age of departure from the nest are characterized by strong inter-countries heterogeneity (Aassve *et al.*, 2002, 2010) affected by differences in labour market conditions and by differences in the unemployment rate. In this framework, as remarked in the introduction, the Italian situation is striking among European countries for the lateness with which young adults leave the parental home (ISTAT, 2009a; Ongaro, 2001; Eurostat, 2009).

In general, young adults tend to stay longer at home if the choice of leaving increases their poverty risk (Aassve *et al.*, 2007). This is particularly true for individuals belonging to lower social class families and/or living in territorial context with poor job opportunities (Micheli and Rosina, 2009; Benassi and Novello, 2009).

The situation for young Italians in the labor market is such that, compared to their European peers, the low-skilled face the highest risk of unemployment, while the highly skilled have difficulty accessing a job in line with their qualifications.

The Global crisis in 2008 is likely to have worsened these situations. The effects of the economic downturn have interested all developed countries but

mainly impacted on Italy, a country characterized by low levels of GDP growth, high unemployment rates (especially among youths), low investment on active labour market programmes, high levels of public debt. In particular the financial crisis produced in Italy a further decline in employment rates, with larger job losses among workers with temporary employment contracts (Lin *et al.* 2013) that, as it is well known, are widespread among youths. OECD Employment Outlook (2012) confirmed the greater vulnerability of younger cohorts, especially among individuals with lower levels of education, with a special focus on the Italian context. “Job losses have been concentrated among youth and the low skilled: the rate of long-term unemployment, an indicator of severe labour market distress, has risen very sharply for youth and, to a much lesser extent, for the low-skilled and prime-age men, while it has remained stable for women and skilled workers. Compared to the OECD average, the increase in the long-term unemployment rate was more marked in Italy and less evenly distributed across socio-demographic groups”.

The general decline in employment conditions of young generations has an impact also on their transition to adulthood. Italy is also one of the few countries in Europe without a scheme of national minimum wage and minimum income. This does not help in limiting the increase of the material deprivation rate (which went from 7% to 14% from 2010 to 2012, with a particular impact on children), the condition of the working poor and the protracted dependence of young Italian people on their family of origin.

Focusing on fertility choices, Goldstein *et al.* (2013) show that Southern European countries – characterized by a difficult and unstable entry of young generations in the labour market – registered a decline in the fertility rates at different ages associated with the increasing trend of unemployment rate. Aasve *et al.* (2013) show that the “Great Recession”, in its first phase (2008-2011), increased the value of several vulnerability indicators and mainly penalized the “younger youth”.

All the (few) cited studies investigating the relationship between the economic crisis and the stages of transition to adulthood are based on macro data analyses. The lack of surveys on micro data that are able to capture the effect of the crisis on individual life course trajectories represent a limit for fully evaluating the impact of the “Great Recession”, starting in 2008. In this paper, we aim at giving an original contribution to fill the gap in the literature comparing individual intentions of leaving the parental home before and after the beginning of the crisis. The following section illustrates the peculiarities of our data that will make our analysis possible.

3. DATA

For our analysis we use data from the survey “Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective” carried out by the *National Institute*

of Statistics (ISTAT) and the data from the “Youth Project” collected by the *Toniolo Institute for Advanced Studies* jointly with IPSOS.

“Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective” is the second wave of the longitudinal survey “Family and Social Subjects”, realized with CATI techniques at the beginning of 2007 on a sample of 9,997 people aged between 18 and 64 years at the time of the first interview. The sample has been obtained from a two stages sample design that uses different strategies based on the size of Italian municipalities. Families were drawn without replacement within each municipality with the same probability. The described procedure generated in 2003 a sample of about 24,000 families: within this collective sample in 2007 the final subsample of 9,997 cases was selected (more details in ISTAT, 2009b).

“Family and Social Subjects” is used in our study to provide information on the social characteristics of Italian young people and their plans for the future just before the beginning of the so-called “Great Recession”. As we aim to evaluate how the recent crisis has affected the transition to adulthood of Italian young adults, micro-data from this survey are compared to those from the “Youth Project” survey, promoted by the “Toniolo Institute for Advanced Studies” and carried out by Ipsos in 2012. 9,087 individuals were drawn from a universe of 7,823,907 young Italian adults aged between 18 and 29 and resident in Italy at 1st January 2011. The sample has been drawn with stratified sampling techniques based on the following variables: age, gender, educational level, employment status, combining information about five macro-areas and municipalities. Then the sampled individuals were interviewed with a mixed procedure that uses CAWI and CATI techniques (for more details see the Appendix in Istituto Giuseppe Toniolo, 2013). The main difference between the two surveys is that the sample unit is the family in “Family and Social Subjects” and the individual in the “Youth project”, nevertheless both are representative at the individual level for the same sub-population of interests in this paper.

Both surveys included standard questions on the intentions regarding the exit from the parental home and plans of family formation, such as marriage and childbearing. They share a common set of questions on the characteristics of the family of origin and on the socio-economic background of the respondents.

The two sources of data present also dissimilarities. A correct empirical methodology should compare samples on a common support with respect to the age of the respondents. Hence, we took into consideration a subset of individuals that are represented in both the samples, reducing the analysis only to people between 21 and 29 years old in the two surveys. Therefore, our final sample includes 7,534 respondents (6,366 from the “Youth project” and 1,168 from “Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective”) for whom we examined the evolution of the intentions before and after the beginning of the Great Recession.

People interviewed in 2007 were asked to indicate their short-term expectations of home leaving with the destination of the respondent: the question is *Do you intend to leave the parental home in the next three years?* Then, a second question asked to clarify the reasons for desiring the residential autonomy in the next three years.

With respect to the “Youth Project” the wording is slightly different: *Do you intend to leave the parental home to live alone or with friends in the next three years?*

As we can see, this formulation leaves out those who want to exit in order to enter in a co-residential partnership. In order to avoid a bias in the response of these questions, we decided to combine the item on the intentions to exit to live alone with the two questions asking whether the individual intends to get married or to start a non-marital cohabitation within the next three years.

Table 1 – *Measures for Intentions*

Measures of interest	2007: Family and social subjects	2012: Youth project
Intentions of leaving the parental home (surely yes, probably yes =1; surely not, probably not=0)	<i>Do you intend to leave the parental home in the next three years? (for marriage, cohabitation, work or study, or to become autonomous)</i>	<i>Do you intend to leave the parental home to live alone or with friends in the next three years? Do you intend to marry in the next three years? Do you intend to start a marital cohabitation in the next three years?</i>

For all the set of questions discussed in this section the four comparable options were: *surely not, probably not, probably yes and surely yes*¹. For the empirical analysis, we decided to group together the responses, precisely *surely not* and *probably not* on one side and *probably yes* and *surely yes* on the other side.

4. METHOD

The aim of the empirical analysis is to explore whether the recent crisis is connected with a delay in the positive intentions of leaving the parental home. Hence, we are in the presence of a binary outcome for the main equations,

¹ In the second round of “Family and Social Subjects” that took place in 2007, 149 cases that answered “I don’t know” to the intentions of leaving the parental home were observed.

taking value one if the respondent intended to exit from the parental home within three years from the time of the interview and zero otherwise.

However, some of the individuals in the sample did not answer the question “Do you intend to leave the parental home in the next three years?”, because they had left the parental home before the beginning of the interview.

We are in the presence of “sample selection”: the expression of the intentions is limited only to those living at home at the time of the interview. Excluding this category may generate a bias in statistical estimates (Heckman 1976).

As we have a binary response outcome (the intentions), we adopt a two-equation modeling strategy, using a binomial probit with sample selection (Van de Ven and Van Praag, 1981) instead of the traditional Heckman sample selection regression, that is implemented for only continuous outcome. The sample data are composed by individuals aged 21-29 in 2007 or 2012. Using a latent variable approach, the model is specified as follows:

$$y_{1j}^* = \beta_{10} + year_j \beta_{11} + \mathbf{x}_{1j}^T \beta_{12} + u_{1j}$$

$$y_{2j}^* = \beta_{20} + year_j \beta_{21} + \mathbf{x}_{2j}^T \beta_{22} + u_{2j}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_{1j} \\ u_{2j} \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho \\ \rho & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$$

y_{1j}^* is the dependent variable of the main regression, indicating the propensity of observing the positive intentions of leaving away from the parental home. As remarked above, only those that were in the parental home at the time of the interview may have answered the question regarding the intentions of exiting; hence, y_{2j}^* , that is the dependent variable for the selection equation, indicates whether a respondent j , still lived in the parental home. In probit with sample selection standard setting y_{1j}^* is observed only if $y_{2j}^* > 0$. The coefficient ρ indicates whether there is a correlation between the errors of the two models. When ρ is equal to zero, the main and selection equations can be estimated independently. When ρ is different from zero the selection mechanism based on unobservables has to be taken into account.

The set of explanatory variables mainly includes a dummy that takes value 1 if an individual is drawn from the 2012 sample and zero if s/he belongs to the 2007 sample. This variable, which is indicated in the model with $year_j$ captures the effect of the global crisis through the coefficient β_{11} , net of the effect of the other covariates included in the model. The crisis dummy has been introduced also in selection equation, in order to control for the heterogeneity between “Family and social subjects” and “Youth project” before estimating the coefficient of the main equation.

Because this item has not a correspondence in the “Youth Project”, we decided to exclude that category from the final regression. A robustness check that includes those cases in the analysis does not change the results of the paper.

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for conditional frequencies of both positive and negative intentions, given the year of the interview.

Table 2 – *Conditional distribution of the dependent variable, given the year of survey.*

Intentions of home leaving	2007	2012
	Family and Social Subjects	Youth project
Positive	0.710	0.646
Negative	0.289	0.353
Total	1.000	1.000

As displayed in Table 2, the percentage of individuals positively intentioned to leave home decreases in 2012, with respect to 2007. However, this result has to be tested in the model presented above, controlling for a set of covariates. The vector of controls for the main equation includes the following variables instead:

- *Gender* of respondents: we decided to introduce a variable for identifying the effect of gender on the intentions of leaving home. considering that the trajectories characterizing to the transition to adulthood are very different for men and women (Andres and Adamuti-Trache, 2008), with a postponement of home leaving for men in Italy with respect to women (Rusconi, 2004; Chiuri and Del Boca, 2010),
- *Age* of respondents: this is a control variable. We grouped the individuals in three age classes: 21-23 (reference category), 24-26 and 27-29.
- *Education*: we distinguish young adults who hold a university degree (bachelor, master or Ph. D) from those that achieved an upper secondary education and from a residual group including those that have lower levels of education.
- *Parents' education*: a variable that summarizes the education level of both the parents at the time of the interview. We decided to combine them in a unique set of categories for substantial reasons but also in order to avoid collinearity problems. Following Migliavacca *et al.* (2015) and using the identical information collected in the two surveys, we considered the following categories: the first one includes the respondents that have at least one parent with a university degree; the second one included the individuals with both the parents with qualification lower than an upper secondary school diploma. Finally, the last category incorporates all the remaining combinations. Parents' education is crucial in our study because it is a proxy of the social class of the individual.
- *Past experiences outside the parental home of more than 3 months*: this variable is present in both surveys with the same time horizon (at least three months outside from the parental home). We can anticipate that individuals experiencing a prolonged autonomy from the parental home are more likely to be intentioned to leave the nest finally.

- *Region of residence*: it is a control variable introduced in order to take into account the geographical heterogeneity and the impact of unobservable context variables. The respondents are classified in four areas: Northeast, Northwest, Centre, South and Islands. In the original sample of “Youth Project” there was an additional fifth area grouping all individuals who lived abroad at the time of interview. In order to build a homogenous category with “Family and social subjects” we decided to drop the individuals residing abroad.
- *Employment status*: a crucial variable that is the main source of the material resources that each individual can have access to in order to become independent. We consider five categories: students (reference category), unemployed, fixed term employees (with a temporary job), permanently employees and self-employed (a category including young entrepreneurs and freelancers). Because the unemployed are not the students in our sample (Alfieri *et al.*, 2015) and due to the age of sampled individuals, we may refer to these individuals also as NEETs (Not in Education, Employment or Training). The problem concerning the inclusion of employment status in \mathbf{x}_{1j}^T is the possible presence of collinearity with the year of observation. More in details, the probability of being employed depends on the macro-economic context. Since in our model the effect of the crisis is captured by a dummy variable, there is the risk that putting in the same model the year indicator and employment status undermines the estimates. As a robustness check, we compare the effect of crisis dummy in a model without controlling for the employment status with the effect in a model with the employment status among the covariates.

All the listed variables represent the controls of the main equation of our model. However, we need to specify also the explanatory variables \mathbf{x}_{2j}^T for the selection equation. Although the sample-selection models may be identified also whether selection and main equation have identical covariates, the applied literature (Cameron and Trivedi, 2005) suggests that the selection model should add at least one variable that is not included in the main equation: hence, \mathbf{x}_{1j}^T and \mathbf{x}_{2j}^T have a different specification in this framework. Based on previous studies, past experiences outside the parental home were omitted from the selection equation, while we added the demographic size of municipality in the set of covariates (see Billari and Liefbroer, 2007), distinguishing whether a respondent lived in a city with more than 10,000 inhabitants or less. The threshold of 10,000 inhabitants has been chosen because in the “Youth project” and in “Family and social subjects” the categorization of the size of the demographic municipality used in sampling procedure is differently summarized in categories; the only common threshold allowing for homogeneously splitting both the samples in two groups is 10,000. Finally, following Aassve *et al.* (2002), age in the selection equation is included as a continuous item.

We described in Table 3 the explanatory variable.

Table 3 – *Summary Statistics of the explanatory variables, by intentions*

Explanatory Variables	Freq. of observations	Freq. of positive intentions	Freq. still living at home
<i>Year</i>			
2007	0.155	0.710	0.791
2012	0.845	0.646	0.860
<i>Gender</i>			
Females	0.512	0.715	0.784
Males	0.488	0.596	0.820
<i>Past experience away from parental home</i>			
No	0.234	0.643	0.969
Yes	0.766	0.743	0.417
<i>Age</i>			
21-23	0.355	0.558	0.898
24-26	0.352	0.693	0.809
27-29	0.293	0.761	0.675
<i>Employment Status</i>			
Student	0.348	0.622	0.876
Unemployed	0.182	0.650	0.795
Fixed term employed	0.188	0.693	0.769
Permanently employed	0.205	0.684	0.761
Self employed	0.079	0.723	0.727
<i>Parent' education</i>			
Lower education for both parents	0.434	0.636	0.787
Other	0.380	0.670	0.824
Higher education for at least one parent	0.186	0.671	0.788
<i>Respondent's Education</i>			
< Upper Secondary	0.224	0.549	0.739
Upper Secondary	0.495	0.642	0.843
Higher	0.282	0.761	0.778
<i>Geographical area</i>			
North West	0.233	0.672	0.791
North East	0.177	0.620	0.802
Centre	0.186	0.650	0.763
South and Islands	0.404	0.654	0.834
<i>Demographic size of Municipality</i>			
< 10000 inhabitants	0.488	0.654	0.804
≥ 10000 inhabitants	0.512	0.657	0.799
Observations	7,534	3,868	5,891

The first column indicates the set of covariates, while the second shows the frequency of individuals within each category. The third column indicates the frequency of individuals being intentioned to leave home (the dependent variable of the main equation) within each category, while the last one indicates the percentage of individuals that still lives with their parents (the dependent variable of the selection equation) at the time of interview for each category.

5. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Results of the regression analyses are presented in Table 4. The first two columns (“Probit 1” and “Probit 2”) display the estimates of the coefficients of simple probit regressions, while the last ones (“Heckman 1” and “Heckman 2”) show the results for both the main and selection equation of probit models with sample selection.

Focusing on the model “Heckman 2”, illustrated in the previous section with the most complete specification, the results from the selection equation those we expected for gender and age. Males tend to live longer than females in the family of origin. Age, introduced in the selection equation as a continuous variable, has the expected negative sign: the older the individual, the lower is the probability of living in co-residence with the parents.

Parents’ educational level shows, net of other covariates, a reversed U-shaped relationship. Individuals both from a family with high socio-cultural resources and belonging to the lower social classes are more likely to reach the residential autonomy².

Concerning the effect of the demographic size of municipality, we found that the effect is significant and positive: in other words, people belonging to small towns are more likely to live still in the parental home. This result supports the assumption that the variable is a relevant instrument for strengthening the identification requirements of the model.

Focusing on the results of the main equation, we obtain empirical evidence of a significant impact of education in the intention of leaving the parental home. The presence of experiences away from the parental home for a period greater than three months also positively affects the probability of being intentioned to leave away.

Some interesting results concern also the role of the family of origin. Individuals whose parents have a low level of education are less likely to be intending to leave the parental home. This result, which is coherent with the literature, may be interpreted jointly with the one from the selection equation. Individuals belonging to lower social classes try to experience residential autonomy before the others, probably even if the salary level is not satisfactory. Nevertheless, youths belonging to lower classes who, for some reasons, fail to live independently are also those who are more penalized and with more difficulties to project an autonomous life.

² p-value of “Lower education for both parents” in the selection equation is close to 0.15.

Table 4 – Estimates of the coefficients of standard probit and sample selection probit models on the intentions of leaving the parental home (2007-2012)

Explanatory variables	Probit 1		Probit 2		Heckman 1		Heckman 2	
	Main equation	Selection equation						
<i>Year</i>								
2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2012	-0.192 ***	-0.168 ***	-0.244 ***	-0.267 ***	-0.221 ***	-0.268 ***		
<i>Gender</i>								
Females	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Males	-0.301 ***	-0.324 ***	-0.220 ***	0.167 ***	-0.248 ***	0.168 ***		
<i>Past experience away from parental home</i>								
No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yes	0.197 ***	0.186 ***	0.177 ***	-0.146 ***	0.170 ***	-0.146 ***		
<i>Age</i>								
21-23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24-26	0.307 ***	0.267 ***	0.168 ***	0.146 ***	0.146 **	0.146 **		
27-29	0.523 ***	0.446 ***	0.200 *	0.162				
<i>Parents' education</i>								
Lower education for both parents	-0.054	-0.081 **	-0.060	-0.057	-0.083 **	-0.057		
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Higher education for at least one parent	-0.034	0.002	-0.078 *	-0.171 ***	-0.043	-0.170 ***		
<i>Respondent's Education</i>								
< Upper Secondary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Upper Secondary	0.226 ***	0.285 ***	0.292 ***	0.283 ***	0.340 ***	0.288 ***		
Higher	0.389 ***	0.448 ***	0.440 ***	0.331 ***	0.491 ***	0.335 ***		

Table 4 – *Cont'd*

<i>Explanatory variables</i>	Probit 1		Probit 2		Heckman 1		Heckman 2	
	Main equation		Main equation		Main equation	Selection equation	Main equation	Selection equation
<i>Region</i>								
North West	0		0		0	0	0	0
North East	0.046		0.015		0.006	-0.149 ***	-0.017	-0.148 ***
Centre	-0.117 **		-0.149 ***		-0.140 ***	-0.131 ***	-0.168 ***	-0.130 ***
South and Islands	-0.037		-0.061		-0.098 **	-0.226 ***	-0.114 **	-0.226 ***
<i>Employment Status</i>								
Student			0				0	
Unemployed			0.149 ***				0.134 ***	
Fixed term employed			0.235 ***				0.213 ***	
Permanently employed			0.238 ***				0.207 ***	
Self employed			0.320 ***				0.279 ***	
<i>Demographic size of Municipality</i>								
< 10000 inhabitants						0		0
≥ 10000 inhabitants						0.055		0.057 *
Intercept	0.293 ***		0.158 *		0.159 **	4.562 ***	0.047	4.555 ***
ρ					0.685 ***		0.639 ***	
Observations	5,891		5,891		7,385	7,385	7,385	7,385

Note: *** significant at 0.01 level, ** significant at 0.05 level, * significant at 0.1 level.

For what concerns the role of the employment status, we find that self-employed individuals are the category that is most likely to have positive intentions to reach the goal of a residential autonomy in comparison to Italian students (Billari *et al.*, 2008) but also in comparison to young people with a fixed or permanent-term contract. Unemployed individuals tend to present higher positive intentions of leaving the parental home than students, but are more similar, at least in the intentions, to the employed.

Our main interest is on the variable “Year of Survey 2012” that results to be strongly significant with a negative sign. Net of all the other covariates, this result provides empirical evidence that young people interviewed in 2012 are less likely to plan to leave the parental home than those interviewed in 2007. This is coherent with a negative impact of the economic crisis that started to show their effects in Italy after 2008.

This finding is even more relevant considering that the effect operates after having controlled for the employment status. The result may be interpreted as a signal that there is an effect of the crisis independent of the effect of the working condition.

The sense of uncertainty may undermine the expectations of the individuals toward the future.

In addition, we check the robustness of the findings running a Heckman probit with and without each explanatory variable in order to evaluate the effect of the crisis dummy. In the column named “Heckman 1” we show that the negative impact of the variable “year 2012” significantly persists, also omitting the employment status.

Finally, we executed also simple probit regressions with or without working conditions, confirming the negative effect of economic crisis, although the ρ coefficients are significantly different from zero in “Heckman 1” and “Heckman 2”, stating the useful specification of a sample selection model. Results of standard probit models also confirm a significant impact of the crisis in reducing the intentions of leaving the parental home in 2012.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we investigated the determinants of intentions of leaving the family of origin, with a specific interest in evaluating the impact of the Great Recession. We combined data drawn from the survey “Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective” carried out by the National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) and the data from the survey “Youth Project” carried out in the mid-2012 by the Toniolo Institute for Advanced Studies and IPSOS. We found, net of other covariates, empirical evidence of a negative impact of the Economic Crisis on the intentions to leave the parental home.

Our result indicates that not only youth unemployment, but also the general climate of uncertainty and insecurity may hinder the transition process to an

autonomous adult life, especially in a familialistic country with a non-existent public welfare system (Rosina *et al.* 2007, Barbieri 2011). There still is a cultural resistance in Italy in considering the young generations as a public good in which to invest wisely, in opposition to the generous private help provided from Italian parents to their own children.

The combination between structural Italian generational disadvantages and the economic insecurity exacerbated by the recent economic crisis particularly increases the risk of a “lost generation” (IMF, 2015). The improvement in employment opportunities and the support towards an autonomous life path for the young generations should be considered a national priority. Italy should adopt every effort in planning and implementing successful measures to support its younger generations in fulfilling their life goals. Our results, however, suggest that only with a different macro-economic context of sustained economic growth it will be actually possible for all these microeconomic policy interventions to be effective. This will require, in turn, expansionary fiscal and monetary policy at the EU level, if not at the country level, to stimulate growth in the long-run (Pastore, 2015).

A limitation of our analysis is the use of two independent surveys, before and during the crisis. In order to study the effect of the economic crisis on the transition to adulthood the best data are those coming from longitudinal surveys. Unfortunately, there is a lack in Italy of data following the life course of young generations. The recent exception is the longitudinal surveys “Family and Social Subjects”, carried out within the GGS (Gender and Generation Surveys) project by the Italian National Institute of Statistics (Istat) in 2003 and with a second panel wave in 2007. Analogous panel data after the beginning of the crisis are not available.

The “Youth Project” of the Toniolo Institute is starting a new survey in 2015 adopting a panel perspective. This will allow a more in-depth analysis on the effects of the crisis and on the life paths of the young generations at the end of the crisis. It can provide some useful information to evaluate the possible improvement in job opportunities, the emergence of a more favorable climate, and its impact on the transition to adulthood.

References

- AASSVE A., COTTINI E., VITALI A. (2013), “Youth prospects in a time of economic recession”, *Demographic Research*, 29(36): 949-962.
- AASSVE A., BILLARI F.C., MAZZUCO S., ONGARO F. (2002), “Leaving Home: A Comparative Analysis of ECHP Data”, *Journal of European Social Policy*, 12(4): 259–275.

- AASSVE A., DAVIA M.A., IACOVOU M., MAZZUCCO S. (2007), “Does Leaving Home Make You Poor? Evidence from 13 European countries”, *European Journal of Population*, 23, 315-338.
- AASSVE A., ARPINO B., BILLARI F.C. (2010), “Age Norms on Leaving Home: Multilevel Evidence from the European Social Survey” *Dondena Working Papers No. 32*, www.dondena.unibocconi.it/wp32.
- AJZEN I. (1991), “The theory of planned behavior”, *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211.
- ALFIERI S., ROSINA A., SIRONI E., MARTA E., MARZANA D. (2015), “Who are Italian “NEETS”? Trust in institutions, political engagement, willingness to be activated and attitudes toward the future in a group at risk for social exclusion”, *Rivista Internazionale di Scienze Sociali*, 123(3): 285-306.
- ANDRES L., ADAMUTI-TRACHE M. (2008), “Life-course transitions, social class, and gender: A 15-year perspective of the lived lives of Canadian young adults”, *Journal of Youth Studies*, 11, 115-145.
- BARBIERI P. (2011), “Italy: no country for young men (and women)”, In BUCHHOLZ S., HOFACKER D. (eds.), *The Flexibilization of European Labor Markets: The Development of Social Inequalities in an Era of Globalization*, Cheltenham, UK/Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar.
- BENASSI D., NOVELLO D. (2009), “The Evolution of Models for Leaving the Family of Origin in Five Italian Urban Areas”, *Italian Journal of Social Policy*, 6(1): 295-307.
- BILLARI F.C., ROSINA A., RANALDI R., ROMANO C. (2008), “Young adults living apart and together (LAT) with parents: A three level analysis of the Italian case”, *Regional Studies*, 42(5): 625-639.
- BILLARI F.C., LIEFBROER A.C. (2007), “Should I Stay or Should I Go? The Impact of Age Norms on Leaving Home”, *Demography*, 44(1): 181-198.
- CAMERON A.C., TRIVEDI P. K. (2005), *Microeconometrics: Methods and Applications*, Cambridge University Press, New York.
- CARCILLO A., FERNÁNDEZ R., KÖNIGS S., MINEA A. (2015), “NEET Youth in the Aftermath of the Crisis. Challenges and Policies”, OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers, No. 164, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- CHIURI M.C., DEL BOCA D. (2010), “Home-leaving decisions of daughters and sons” *Review of Economics of the Household* 8(3): 393-408.
- DE LONG GIERVELD J., LIEFBROER A.C., BEEKINK E. (1991), “The Effect of Parental Resources on Patterns of Leaving Home among Young Adults in the Netherlands”, *European Sociological Review*, 7(1): 55-71.
- DE MARCO A.C., COSNER BERZIN S. (2008), “The Influence of Family Economic Status on Home-Leaving Patterns During Emerging Adulthood”, *Family in Society: The Journal of Contemporary Social Services*, 89(2): 208-218.

- DALLA ZUANNA G. (2001), "The banquet of Aeolus: A familistic interpretation of Italy's lowest low fertility", *Demographic Research*, 4, 133-162.
- DALLA ZUANNA G., MICHELI G.A. (2004), "*Strong family and low fertility: a paradox? New perspective in interpreting contemporary family and reproductive behavior*", Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- DI GIULIO P., ROSINA A. (2007), "Intergenerational family ties and the diffusion of cohabitation in Italy", *Demographic Research*, 16, 441-468.
- EUROSTAT (2009), *Youth in Europe. A statistical portrait*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- EUROSTAT (2015), *Being young in Europe today - family and society*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- FERRARI G., ROSINA A., SIRONI E. (2014), "Beyond Good Intentions: The Decision-Making Process of Leaving the Family of Origin in Italy", *Dondena Working Paper*, 60, 1-23.
- FISHBEIN M., AJZEN I. (1975), *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: Introduction to Theory and Research*, Reading MA, Addison Wesley.
- GINIC. (1909), "Il Diverso Accrescimento delle Classi Sociali e la Concentrazione della Ricchezza", *Giornale degli Economisti*, 38(1): 27-83.
- GOLDSHEIDER F., GOLDSHEIDER C. (1993), *Leaving Home Before Marriage: Ethnicity, Familism and Generational Relationships*, Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin Press.
- GOLDSTEIN J., KREYENFELD M., JASILIONIENE A., ÖRSAL D.K. (2013), "Fertility Reactions to the "Great Recession" in Europe", *Demographic Research*, 29(4): 85-104.
- HECKMAN J.J. (1976), "The common structure of statistical models of truncation, sample selection and limited dependent variables and a simple estimator for such models" *Annals of Economic and Social Measurement*, 5(4): 475-492.
- HOGAN D.P., ASTONE N.M. (1986), "The Transition to Adulthood" *Annual Review of Sociology*, 12, 109-130.
- IACOVOU M. (2002), "Regional differences in transition to adulthood", *The Annals of American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 580, 40-69.
- IACOVOU M. (2010), "Leaving Home: Independence, togetherness and income in Europe", *Advances in Life Course Events*, 15(4): 147-160.
- IMF (2015), "Euro Area Policies. Selected Issues", Country Report No. 15/205.
- ISTAT (2009a), *Le difficoltà nella transizione dei giovani allo stato adulto e le criticità nei percorsi di vita femminili*, Report Istat on "Critical aspects in the work life course in a gender perspective".
- ISTAT (2009b) *APPENDICE A Strategia di campionamento e livello di precisione dei risultati nell'indagine di ritorno del 2007 "Criticità dei percorsi lavorativi in un'ottica di genere"*, http://www3.istat.it/salastampa/comunicati/non_calendario/20091228_00/note_metodologiche.pdf.

- ISTITUTO GIUSEPPE TONIOLO (2013), *La condizione giovanile in Italia. Rapporto Giovani 2013*, Il Mulino, Bologna.
- LESTHAEGHE R., MOORS G. (2002), Life Course Transition and Value Orientations: Selection and Adaptation, in LESTHAEGHE R., MOORS G. (eds.), *Meaning and Choice: Value Orientations and Life Course Decisions*, NIDI CBGS Publications, 1-38.
- LIN C.Y., EDVINSSON L., CHEN J., BEDING T. (2013), *National Intellectual Capital and the Financial Crisis in Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain*, Springer Briefs in Economics, Springer, Heidelberg.
- MICHELI G.A., ROSINA A. (2009), “The Vulnerability of Young Adults on Leaving the Parental Home”, in RANCI C. (ed.), *Vulnerability in Europe*, London, Palgrave, 189-218.
- MIGLIAVACCA M., ROSINA A., SIRONI E. (2015), “Condizione lavorativa e mobilità internazionale delle nuove generazioni italiane”, *Mondi Migranti*, (2): 53-78.
- OECD (2012), *OECD Employment Outlook 2012*, Report OECD.
- ONGARO F. (2001), “Transition to adulthood in Italy”, in CORIJN M., KLIZING E. (eds.), *Transition to Adulthood in Europe*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht.
- PASTORE F. (2015), “The Youth Experience Gap. Explaining National Differences in the School-to-work Transition”, *Springer Briefs in Economics*, Springer, Heidelberg.
- REHER D. S. (1998), Family Ties in Western Europe: Persistent Contrasts, *Population and Development Review*, 24(2): 203-234.
- ROSINA A., FRABONI R. (2004), “Is marriage losing its centrality in Italy?”, *Demographic Research*, 11 (6): 149-172.
- ROSINA A., MICHELI G.A., MAZZUCCO S. (2007), “An Analysis of Young People’s Risk of Difficulties on Leaving the Parental Home”, *Italian Journal of Social Policy*, 4(3): 95-111.
- RUSCONI A. (2004), “Different Pathways out of the Parental Home: A Comparison of West Germany and Italy”, *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 35(4): 627-649.
- SANTARELLI E., COTTONE F. (2009), “Leaving Home, Family Support and Intergenerational Ties in Italy: Some Regional Differences”, *Demographic Research*, 21, 1-22.
- SWARTZ T.T., KIM M., MORTIMER J., O’BRIEN K.B., “Safety Nets and Scaffolds: Parental Support in the Transition to Adulthood”, *Journal of Marriage and Family* 73(2): 414-429.
- VAN DE VEN W.P.M.M., VAN PRAAG B.M.S. (1981), “The demand of deductibles in private health insurance: a probit model with sample selection”, *Journal of Econometrics*, 17(2): 229-252.